

Feeling touch without touching

How are ultrahaptics going to affect societal virtual interactions in the Metaverse?

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Introduction

During the past years, the world has experienced a shift from reality to virtual tasks to which we have adapted in many ways. During the COVID-19 world pandemic, "consumers have moved drastically towards online channels, and companies and industries have responded in turn" (*McKinsey & Company*). The pandemic also changed habits, reviewed society's values, and accelerated the future, anticipating changes that were already underway. Society has largely benefited from this change, provided by tasks being carried out more immediately, enhanced connectivity across individuals, and reduced pollution due to lower use of transport (*Sung and Monschauer*)(*Okabe-Miyamoto and Lyubomirsky*). However, it all comes with great challenges.

Social interaction has, in a way, decreased (*Tamirisa and Co-Vu*). The world is going through a massive loss of spontaneous conversations as our sense and perception of reality have been largely reduced to what was beforehand. Humans are constantly striving to stay close to and interact with each other, suggesting the "need to feel connected and establish emotional bonds with others to create and maintain interpersonal relationships" (Baumeister and Leary).

Out of the many human senses, touch is the only sense that we cannot imagine ourselves without. It is easy to put earplugs in and not hear; close the mouth, and put a tissue around the eyes to simulate blindness. Even certain disorders like anosmia and ageusia, referred to as the loss of the sense of smell and taste respectively, can emerge from

certain diseases and can inhibit both senses from being used in daily lives for a particular period of time (*Johns Hopkins Medicine*). Touch, however cannot be restrained.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the period of social isolation was undoubtedly the only time when the feeling of losing the sense of touch could be most identified. There are indications that people have gotten fatigued due to extended periods of video chats and meetings, seen as they crave human contact (*BBC News*). Their attempt to seek such physical contact, the Metaverse.

The Metaverse

The term Metaverse is not new. It appeared 10 years ago with the work of Neal Stephenson called "Snow Crash", which synchronizes reality and fiction through a video game (*Machado*). In this current moment in time, the Metaverse is commonly referred to as virtual worlds. There isn't the main world, however. In comparison to our reality, our planet, the metaverse allows users to completely immerse themselves in countless worlds, and that is what makes the idea of a Metaverse so fascinating to many.

Inside the Metaverse, people can start living their own 'virtual lives' and achieve the closest level of distanced human interaction. The idea of reflecting on how our current world looks and making it virtual innovates a whole new range of possibilities. "Despite still being in an experimental

stage with only a few platforms available for general use, the unified virtual world of the Metaverse promises limitless opportunities" (*Admin*).

Users are encouraged to socialize and make new friends with the ability to create customizable avatars. This means users can express themselves by being anyone they like, from different hair colors, body types, and gender. Other Metaverse activities include shopping for real and virtual products, attending learning events and concerts or even getting a job. Moreover, the Metaverse opens new economic opportunities that make its interaction even more attractive. Interestingly, real estate is among the most popular reasons people enter the metaverse (*Admin*). Therefore, a person can purchase parcels from a metaverse platform utilizing the world's provided cryptocurrency token that is directly linked to the individual's actual bank account. In this, the metaverse is bringing a new way of joining virtual reality as well as yielding real-world benefits to its users (*Finn*).

Andrew Bosworth, chief technology officer of Meta, described the Metaverse himself as "A spatial construct, as opposed to the previous web". The Metaverse is currently being seen as a different interaction with technology (*Ravenscraft*).

Interdisciplinary Approach

The essay provides an interdisciplinary approach as it focuses on the neuroscientific effects of the use of ultrasonic technology in

diminishing social disconnection and the development of loneliness and psychological diseases. Therefore, biology and psychology were chosen due to their similarity and their complementary effects in addressing the impacts ultrahaptics can have on society. It is not only essential to understand the biological processes of the mammalian sense of touch but also the effects different kinds of touch, like pain, temperature, vibration, and their respective deficiency have in the brain (*GriffinOT*). A biological approach isn't possible without psychology and vice-versa. Investigating how humans are intervening in the biology of the human body and artificially creating touch must incorporate its conceptual understanding of psychology, specifically the pathways necessary for any physical skin contact to be categorized as a tactile stimulus. Moreover, the interaction of both subjects is necessary to establish a holistic approach toward ultrasonic technology.

State of Technology

Currently, there are solely two out of all of the major body senses integrated into virtual reality (VR), namely vision and hearing. The sense of touch is, however, left out and is the sense currently being studied and incorporated in small increments into virtual and augmented reality experiences (*Kowalski*). Users can start to experience slight glimpses of what the technology will look like, but to an extremely confined degree. There are already gloves and actuators being designed, but their purpose

is rather limited to a broad user experience as the technology deviates from immersion and realism (*Singh*). Moreover, there is the development of body actuators, referred to as body suits, for virtual reality, which also helps provide some additional immersion. However, these examples are solely small features that still don't provide the full tactile experience we want to achieve.

The current technology relies primarily on sight and hearing to establish immersion; hence they lack realism (*Singh*). The immersion of VR starts to break down if the sense of touch isn't accurate enough. For instance, you might be able to do a high-five with someone in the Metaverse, which sounds exciting enough, but without the actual feeling of sensing the skin of the hand, the subconscious realization that the hand can go through these virtual objects diminishes the immersion, which can have profound cognitive and emotional after-effects on the user (*Longa et al.*).

The substantial development of digital technologies has attempted to overcome this limiting physical interaction through devices that bring the digital world a step closer to how reality looks and feels, ultrahaptics being one of them (*Marr*). Society will most solely rely on virtual experiences that will reach a verge where it is perhaps nearly impossible to distinguish what is virtual and what is real. To what extent will this be beneficial to society, though? How does artificially stimulating touch redefine societal craving for physical interactions? With the current fast development of the Metaverse, I believe that the race for creating virtual

touch has started. This led to my research question: **How are ultrahaptics going to affect societal virtual interactions in the Metaverse?**

The goal of this Extended Essay will be to explore the technological advancements integrated with the human sensory receptors to gather a better understanding of the under-explored technology of ultrasonic waves. Further, the essay will explore how this technology will ultimately lead to people feeling touch without any physical contact and the impacts this will have on society's interaction with the Metaverse.

The Science of Touch

The skin is the largest organ in the human body (*GriffinOT*). It contains millions of sensory mechanoreceptors that are purposely aimed at the identification of pain, temperature, pressure, and itch. There are different kinds of receptors, and each responds to different stimuli. (See Figure 1).

Figure 1: Diagram of the different mechanoreceptors located throughout the layers of the skin (*Iheanacho and Vellipuram*).

The way we feel touch starts when such mechanoreceptors are deformed. “Anytime you’re interacting with an object, your skin deforms or squishes a bit” (*Kowalski*). Whenever this happens, a chemical signal is sent to the nervous system of the body. Nerve cells (neurons) which are connected underneath the skin, receive these signals from sensory neurons. The chemical signal is then passed along neighboring neurons until it eventually reaches the brain and spinal cord.

Example of a sensory pathway

Say a gentle touch on your right hand's index finger. This is a fine touch and is able to deform mechanoreceptors in the skin. If the stimulus is strong enough, an action potential is generated, allowing for a signal to be transmitted down the hand to the brain. The same neuron travels up the spinal cord until it reaches the brain stem. The first synapse occurs, and a second neuron carries the signal forward. First, the neuron will cross the medulla (where the synapse occurs), to its other side. It then keeps moving and reaches the thalamus. Anytime information from the body wants to get to the brain for the person to be aware of it, it must go through the thalamus (*Dr Matt & Dr Mike*). A second synapse will occur in the thalamus, and a third neuron will catch the information first commenced in the index finger and send it to the cortex of the brain that will correspond to the mapping of the individual's respective hand. (See Figure 2).

Figure 2: The cortex of the brain contains sections that correspond to parts of the body. The larger the area, the more susceptible to tactile stimulation (*Alila Medical Media*) (*Simmons*).

How do we feel texture?

Whenever a person slides their finger across any surface, vibrations will travel through the layers of the skin and stimulate the nerve endings of mechanoreceptors that will excite and transmit an electrical signal to be interpreted by the brain. Different vibrations are created based on the material's texture. This is how the body is able to differentiate between objects and their respective texture.

Each texture produces a set of vibrations and they are different from one texture to another. Luckily these vibrations can be measured, and if they are measured, they can be recreated. This is the first step towards figuring out the reproduction of tactile sensations (*Kowalski*).

Pacinian corpuscles

Pacinian corpuscles are mechanoreceptors found very deep in the skin within the reticular dermis and hypodermis (*A-Level Biology*). It is a highly sensitive receptor and, therefore, is used to detect external stimuli and signal the CNS (central nervous system), meaning they are susceptible to easy reception of pressure and vibration, which is

advantageous for the detection of ultrasonic waves, for instance (*A-Level Biology*).

The way they work consists of the detection of sole pressure and vibration stimuli. Represented by the structure of the pacinian corpuscles in Figure 3, pressure is detected from the position or shape by which the receptor is positioned at. Certain amounts of pressure applied to the outer layer of the skin cause the **lamella**, a thin tissue plate of the pacinian corpuscles, to deform.

Figure 3: Structure of pacinian corpuscle with its system of capsules and central cavity (*A-Level Biology*).

Ultrahaptics

In order for humans to 'touch without touching', such receptors must be stimulated by an external factor. Researchers from the Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory are investigating how sound waves can be used

to create tactile sensations in the human skin (*Moore et al.*). Using ultrasound means that the sound waves are extremely high-pitched, and people can't hear them. The sound waves are strong enough to put pressure on human skin and trigger the sensation of touch (*Ornes*).

Ultrasound stimuli are used to stimulate mechanoreceptors and allow the brain to interpret touch without any physical contact. Initially, their aim was to study the intensity of pleasantness using ultrasonic waves. Using microneurography, the researchers discovered which mechanoreceptors become stimulated by ultrasonic waves. As explained beforehand, receptors become stimulated once a threshold is reached, thus transmitting neuroelectric signals to the brain (*Carter*).

Discriminatory touch involves the perception of touch of different objects and their respective surface texture. The study concluded that low threshold mechanoreceptors (LTMs), like Pacinian corpuscles, are the ones responsible for the interpretation of such sensations. It is found that the glabrous skin, like the palm of the hand, for instance, consists of four different types of low threshold mechanoreceptors. Further, in order to evaluate the effectiveness of ultrasound stimulation, the team carried out the Touch Experience and Attitudes Questionnaire (TEAQ). The experiment consists of the self-reported valuation of pleasantness in reply to ultrasound stimulation. Additionally, by utilizing microneurography, the team identified which low-threshold mechanoreceptors are activated by ultrasonic waves (*Moore et al.*).

Focused ultrasound can, in fact, induce thermal, tactile, tickling, pain, and itching sensations (*Carter*). There are two methods in which ultrasound can be used to generate tactile stimulation. The first method takes advantage of the force generated when the ultrasonic waves are reflected. This method, namely **acoustic radiation force**, is able to be used in order to penetrate the skin and stimulate mechanoreceptors, thus generating a haptic sensation. The second method will completely diverge from mechanoreceptors and stimulate nerve fibers. This method, however demands a more powerful use of acoustic fields and isn't suitable for long-term usage of ultrahaptics (*Carter*).

The First time acoustic radiation force was used to generate tactile sensation was first found by Dalecki. The experiment first started underwater, where an ultrasound transducer was used to radiate ultrasound onto a user's finger. The experiment utilized an appropriate frequency in order to be detected by the receptors in the finger. A change in a water-based to airborne ultrasound demonstrated the potential of the technology for further experiments.

The invention of the term 'ultrahaptics' then originated as a result of the potential this technology has shown and how companies can start to add ultrasound transducer arrays beneath interactive surfaces to create mid-air haptic sensations. This particular arrangement allows the radiation of focused ultrasound onto the user's hands. The reason why an array of ultrasound transducers are used is because of the different feedback points it can create. The ultrasound transducers are able to modulate the

radiated ultrasound as a way of diversifying the sensations a user can feel. Different vibration frequencies enable different tactile properties. Furthermore, when this concept is applied in conjunction with the many ultrasound arrays, a variety of feedback points and sensations can be formed in the user's hand, enabling a range of possible uses of this technology. This means that a user will be able to feel several different regions of the hand as well as the different tactile properties of whatever is being displayed. A range of possibilities is opened up as the user will be able to interact with an entirety of displays and receive live mid-air tactile feedback based on the actions performed (*Vrgineers*).

Evaluation

Despite understanding its functionality, it is worth taking into consideration whether ultrahaptics are able to play a significant role in modulating social presence and interpersonal communication in the Metaverse (*Longa et al.*). The following section critically examines such discussion.

Ultrahaptics in Virtual Worlds

Without the implementation of touch, virtual experiences ultimately become false and empty (*H-Reality*). An application of ultrahaptics can already be seen in H-Reality, a technology company that aims to become

the commercial pioneer with this new technology. The goal is to bring 'non-contact' haptics to virtual reality, enabling users to experience 3D shapes and textures in real space (*H-Reality*). Much more than that, the company aims to use ultrahaptics to transform online interactions by assuring safety in the operation of dangerous machinery as well as surgeries being done fully on 'thin air'.

Looking at the stage of virtual reality at the moment, surveys have been conducted to address whether VR applications bring physical and mental positivity in the first place. Specifically, non-parametric tests were used to assess the statistical significance of responses provided by 646 participants during periods of forced lockdown (*Siani and Marley*). Figure 4 below shows that the majority of participants with access to virtual reality headsets responded positively to the usefulness of VR for their mental health.

Figure 4: Percentage of respondents reporting that VR activities have a positive impact on their mental health on a scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree)(*Siani and Marley*).

On the other hand, whilst virtual realities can easily satisfy social needs, sometimes extensive usage can lead users to withdraw physically from society (*Kim*). Just like with other technologies, there will be drawbacks associated with its overuse. Although physical responses such as dizziness and nausea commonly occur, these subside quicker, whereas mental and psychological impacts can be much more significant and long-lasting (*Berger*).

Two more studies were conducted to investigate cognitive performance as well as negative rumination coming from VR usage. Study 1 was designed to identify the negative effects of the technology on its users through the means of a survey, whilst study 2 studied the brain responses of participants with and without a virtual reality headset (*Berger*)(*Lavoie et al.*). The first study only provided partial support for the research as it mainly targeted user-generated responses about their experiences within the VR world itself (*Lavoie et al.*). Nonetheless, of the 138 participants surveyed, 34 (35.42%) reported strong negative experiences after the VR experience had ended. The overall results of the survey imply that the current state of VR (without any tactile, haptic sensation) intensified negative emotions (*Lavoie et al.*). This means the

actual presenceness in a virtual environment was the key factor in intensifying feelings such as anxiety and fear.

Study two further supports this claim by putting participants in a low-stress game scenario in order to recognize the different absorption levels between the 2D laptop experience against virtual reality. The results of this study showed that the groups did indeed differ in absorption levels, with those in VR being more absorbed than the group in the computer condition (*Lavoie et al.*).

Hence, the high absorption levels intensified negative emotional feedback, denoting the potential psychological consequences resulting from the use of this technology (*Berger*)(*Lavoie et al.*). What is more, from the use of a flow absorption subscale to measure absorption levels in this study, many of the items followed "I lost track of time" or "I was completely absorbed in the experience", which very well contributes to the factor of addictiveness VR brings to its users (*Lavoie et al.*).

A paper released about timing and time compression reveals that time is seen to pass at a quicker rate during the usage of virtual reality headsets for gaming (*Mullen and Davidenko*). Two versions of a labyrinth game were designed for VR and conventional monitor groups to explore this effect. The participants themselves were asked to share an estimated guess when 5 minutes of gameplay had passed. Results showed that participants playing in virtual reality conditions played for an average of 72.6 more seconds than the conventional monitor group of participants (*Mullen and Davidenko*). There is a positive correlation between addiction

generated from extensive usage time to decreased mental health, supported by lower life satisfaction and an increase in anxiety levels and depression (*Siani and Marley*).

Thus, a bigger issue is created as society already experiences significant harmful consequences from the usage of virtual reality, and the inclusion of new sensorial technology like ultrahaptics can only enhance its effects.

Connect or Disconnect?

The sense of touch accounts for the most direct and intimate channel of social interactions (*Longa et al.*). The current development of internet-based technologies offers new opportunities for overcoming the desire for physical human interaction. Through the exploration of ultrahaptics, however, such artificial stimulation can, in fact, diminish the feeling of social presence if the immersion is lost (*Longa et al.*). A neuroscientific evaluation of the importance of physical and interpersonal touch is thus essential for making a holistic judgment towards the effectiveness of ultrahaptics in enhancing health and psychological well-being (*Pietromonaco and Collins*).

On one hand, ultrahaptics may take part in one of the major connecting tools, enhancing the realness of communication and presenceness in the Metaverse (*Slater et al.*)(*Riva and Murray*). On the

other hand, research reveals the potential disconnection from one's body, causing a reduction in face-to-face communication due to its inherent addictiveness. Hence, ultrahaptics possess both positive and negative effects on societal virtual interactions in the Metaverse, as many experiences a "paradoxical situation in which mental and virtual mobility counterposes physical distance and social separation" (*Longa et al.*)

(See Figure 5).

Figure 5: Schematic representation of an integrative perspective on the applicability of interpersonal affective touch in virtual reality (VR) as a potential driver of self-other connection (*Longa et al.*).

By observing the way the Metaverse works, it is possible to notice how much this technology can change the way we interact with the digital and physical world, not just in terms of entertainment but in relation to the way we learn, feel and evolve.

Conclusion

At a molecular level, the sense of touch is still the least understood among all senses (*Thompson*). Up until today's lives, it is yet not fully understood how mammals can perceive all kinds of different sensations, much less how this is thoroughly applied in the Metaverse (*Thompson*).

The world pandemic accelerated new technological advancements, ultrahaptics being one of them. The technology revealed promising results for science and society, offering "an innovative and multidisciplinary perspective on the human need for social connection in a world that depends on more and more communication" (*Longa et al.*).

At first sight, Ultrahaptics offers a technological revolution that is undeniable to humans. A touchless gesture-controlled device, able to artificially activate touch receptors, can have a long-lasting impact on how society interacts virtually. However, the technology is still being constantly developed, and several other perspectives and applications can be explored but go beyond what this essay presents. Nonetheless, the interdisciplinary analysis of this technology allows for the holistic conclusion that ultrahaptics help people connect emotionally in a natural way, regardless of distance, and could be the next paradigm shift in societal virtual interactions.

The result of this is a direct influence on people's behavior and lives. After all, it is not a technology that serves only to entertain but to seek alternative means of physical human contact. In this way, it is natural that our attitudes, thoughts, and behaviors as a whole can be

influenced by ultrahaptics, as it is a tool capable of promoting enhanced cognitive and psychological stimulation.

Ultrahaptics cannot substitute real-life physical interactions but can significantly affect the ability to form emotional and meaningful social bonds.

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